

Frequency and Determinant of Premature Menopause among Women Attending the Tertiary Care PMC Hospital

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Article Details

ABSTRACT

Keywords

Premature Menopause; Premature Ovarian Background: Premature menopause, defined as cessation of ovarian function before Insufficiency; Determinants; Prevalence; 40 years, is a critical reproductive health concern associated with infertility, Complications; Osteoporosis; Cardiovascular osteoporosis, cardiovascular disease, and psychological morbidity. Evidence from low- and middle-income countries suggests higher prevalence, but data from Pakistan remain limited. Objective: To determine the frequency and determinants of premature menopause and evaluate its complications among women attending a tertiary care hospital. Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted over six months from 23rd May 2024 to 22nd November 2024, in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Peoples University of Medical & Health Sciences (PUMHS), a tertiary care hospital. Using a non-probability consecutive sampling technique, 200 women aged ≥ 18 years (< 40 years), attending the outpatient department, were enrolled. Data on socio-demographic, reproductive, medical, lifestyle factors, and complications were collected using a structured questionnaire. Analysis was performed in SPSS v25, with descriptive and bivariate statistics applied. Results: The prevalence of premature menopause was 9.0% (18/200). Determinants included urban residence, passive smoking, low diet diversity, low physical activity, autoimmune illness, and prior gynecologic surgery. Complications observed among affected women were higher rates of osteoporosis, ischemic heart disease, and anxiety/depression. Conclusion: The observed prevalence of premature menopause in this Pakistani cohort is higher than global estimates. Findings highlight the need for preventive strategies, including smoking control, nutritional counseling, promotion of physical activity, and early screening. Larger multicenter studies are warranted to inform policy and guide educational interventions tailored to those women at risk..

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INTRODUCTION:

Menopause is defined as the permanent cessation of menstruation resulting from the loss of ovarian follicular activity and is diagnosed retrospectively after twelve consecutive months of amenorrhea. Globally, the mean age of menopause is around 50 years, with most women experiencing it between 45 and 55 years¹. When menopause occurs before the age of 40, it is referred to as premature menopause, or more precisely, premature ovarian insufficiency (POI). This condition is characterized by persistent amenorrhea or oligomenorrhea, hypoestrogenism, and elevated gonadotropins, reflecting early depletion or dysfunction of the ovarian reserve^{2,3}.

The occurrence of premature menopause is clinically and socially significant. Women affected by POI face an abrupt and irreversible loss of fertility, a factor that carries substantial psychosocial consequences, especially in societies where reproduction plays a central role in defining female identity. Beyond infertility, the early decline in estrogen levels is linked to multiple long-term health consequences, including accelerated bone loss and osteoporosis, increased risk of cardiovascular disease, metabolic disturbances, and premature mortality⁴⁻⁶. Furthermore, premature menopause is associated with vasomotor symptoms, urogenital atrophy, and impaired sexual function. The psychological burden is considerable, with higher rates of depression, anxiety, reduced self-esteem, and overall diminished quality of life compared to women experiencing natural menopause at the expected age⁷.

Globally, premature menopause affects about 1% of women under 40 years, while early menopause (between 40 and 45 years) is observed in nearly 5% of women⁸. However, prevalence varies widely depending on geographic region, ethnicity, socioeconomic conditions, and access to healthcare. In low- and middle-income countries, environmental exposures, malnutrition, and limited reproductive healthcare services contribute to higher rates of early ovarian insufficiency⁹. Recent global analyses have also highlighted secular trends suggesting a decline in the average age of menopause in resource-limited settings, further underscoring the need for region-specific data¹⁰.

The etiology of premature menopause is multifactorial. Genetic predisposition plays a recognized role, with a strong association seen in women with a family history of early menopause. Autoimmune mechanisms, particularly thyroid and adrenal disorders, are also well-established contributors. Iatrogenic causes such as bilateral oophorectomy, pelvic radiation, and gonadotoxic chemotherapy are important determinants in both developed and developing countries^{2,4}. In addition, lifestyle factors such as cigarette smoking, low body mass index, and nutritional deficiencies have been consistently linked with increased risk¹¹. Despite this, the relative contribution of these factors varies by population, highlighting the need for local studies.

In Pakistan, research on premature menopause remains scarce. A cross-sectional study conducted in interior Sindh reported associations with poor nutrition, low socioeconomic status, multiparity, and early marriage, pointing to unique socio-demographic determinants in this setting¹². However, institutional-level data are limited, particularly from tertiary care centers that serve as referral hubs for diverse populations. This gap hinders the development of contextually relevant prevention, early diagnosis, and management strategies.

The present study seeks to answer the research question: What is the frequency of premature menopause and what are its determinants among women attending a tertiary care hospital in Pakistan?

The main objective is to determine the prevalence of premature menopause and to identify its associated factors in this population. By generating local evidence, this study aims to fill a critical

knowledge gap and contribute to the formulation of preventive guidelines and health interventions tailored for women at risk of premature menopause in Pakistan.

METHODS

Study Design & Setting

This was a hospital-based cross-sectional quantitative study conducted at the Department of Obstetrics & Gynecology, PUMHS Hospital, Shaheed Benazirabad, a tertiary care center. The study duration was six months, from 23-05-2024 to 22-11-2024.

Study Population & Sampling

Target population: Women aged ≥ 18 years attending the Gynecology OPD during the study period.

Inclusion criteria: Women aged ≥ 18 years, attending OPD, willing to participate (consent).

Exclusion criteria: Women with surgical menopause (bilateral oophorectomy), prior chemotherapy or pelvic radiotherapy, and those declining participation.

Sampling technique: Non-probability consecutive sampling until the sample size was reached.

Sample size: The sample size is calculated as 200 by using the WHO sample size determination software

Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire (English/Urdu), completed by participants in the OPD waiting area. Variables included:

- Outcome: Premature menopause (cessation of menses before 40 years, defined as ≥ 12 months of amenorrhea before age 40).
- Determinants: Sociodemographic (age, education, residence, socioeconomic status), reproductive (age at menarche, parity, abortions, breastfeeding), medical (autoimmune illnesses, gynecologic surgeries, chronic diseases), and lifestyle (smoking, dietary habits, physical activity).

DATA ANALYSIS:

Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics included prevalence with 95% confidence intervals, frequencies and percentages for categorical variables, and mean \pm standard deviation (or median with interquartile range) for continuous variables. Chi-square test (or Fisher's exact test where applicable) was used to examine associations between determinants and premature menopause. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations:

The study, was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of PUMHS. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants. Data confidentiality was maintained through anonymous study IDs, and participation was voluntary without any impact on patient care.

RESULTS

Data from 200 women were analyzed. Analyses were conducted in SPSS version 25. Continuous variables are presented as mean \pm SD and median [IQR], and categorical variables as n (%).

Overall, 18 women (9.0%) were identified with premature menopause (Figure 1).

Table 1 summarizes demographic and reproductive characteristics. The mean age was 38.2 ± 8.3 years; mean age at menarche 13.1 ± 1.2 years; mean parity 1.8 ± 1.4 ; mean abortions 0.4 ± 0.6 ; and mean cumulative breastfeeding 10.9 ± 10.1 months.

Table 2 shows categorical distributions including residence, education, socioeconomic status, smoking, diet diversity, physical activity, autoimmune illness, chronic disease, gynecologic surgery, and PM status.

Determinants of PM (Figure 2) showed higher category-specific PM percentages among rural residents, passive smoking exposure, low diet diversity, and low physical activity; autoimmune

illness and prior gynecologic surgery also exhibited elevated PM percentages.

Complications (Figure 3) were more common among women with PM than without PM: osteoporosis, ischemic heart disease, and positive anxiety/depression screen all showed higher percentages in the PM group, highlighting the health burden associated with premature menopause.

Table 1: Demographic and Reproductive Characteristics (N=200)

Variable	Mean ± SD	Median [IQR]
Age years	38.2 ± 8.3	38.0 [32.0–44.0]
Age at Menarche years	13.1 ± 1.2	13.1 [12.5–13.9]
Parity	1.8 ± 1.4	2.0 [1.0–3.0]
Abortions	0.4 ± 0.6	0.0 [0.0–1.0]
Breastfeeding Months	10.9 ± 10.1	8.0 [3.0–17.2]

Table 2: Categorical Characteristics (N=200)

Variable	Distribution n (%)
Residence	Rural: 121 (60.5%); Urban: 79 (39.5%)
Education	Secondary: 81 (40.5%); Primary: 48 (24.0%); None: 39 (19.5%); College+: 32 (16.0%)
SES	Middle: 92 (46.0%); Low: 85 (42.5%); High: 23 (11.5%)
Smoking Status	Never: 140 (70.0%); Passive: 47 (23.5%); Active: 13 (6.5%)
Diet Diversity	Moderate: 99 (49.5%); Low: 73 (36.5%); High: 28 (14.0%)
Physical Activity	Moderate: 96 (48.0%); Low: 71 (35.5%); High: 33 (16.5%)
Autoimmune Illness	No: 191 (95.5%); Yes: 9 (4.5%)
Chronic Disease	None: 104 (52.0%); Hypertension: 38 (19.0%); Diabetes: 28 (14.0%); Thyroid: 15 (7.5%); Multiple: 15 (7.5%)
Gyne Surgery NonOoph	No: 181 (90.5%); Yes: 19 (9.5%)
Premature Menopause	No: 182 (91.0%); Yes: 18 (9.0%)

Premature Menopause Prevalence (N=200)

Figure 1. Prevalence of premature menopause (N=200)

Figure 2. Determinants: category-specific % PM (combined)

Figure 3. Complications by PM status

DISCUSSION

This study assessed the frequency and determinants of premature menopause among women attending a tertiary care hospital in Pakistan. We found a prevalence of **9.0%**, which is notably higher than the global estimate of approximately 1% for women under 40 years and 5% for early menopause before 45 years⁸. This discrepancy may reflect contextual factors in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), such as nutritional deficiencies, environmental stressors, limited access to reproductive health care, and socioeconomic disparities⁹. Previous data from interior Sindh similarly suggested higher-than-expected rates, supporting the likelihood of a real regional burden¹².

Our findings identified several determinants associated with premature menopause. Women residing in rural areas exhibited a higher relative proportion of cases of rural women forming the majority of the sample. This seems to be against the reports, linking urban residence to lifestyle-related risk factors, including increased stress, dietary transitions, and higher exposure to environmental pollutants¹³. Similarly, **passive smoking** emerged as a relevant factor. Tobacco exposure has long been recognized as an accelerator of ovarian follicle depletion and an established

determinant of early menopause¹⁴.

Low Diet Diversity was associated with elevated rates of premature menopause in our cohort. Poor nutritional status and inadequate intake of phytoestrogen-rich foods may contribute to early depletion of ovarian reserve, consistent with studies in LMIC populations¹⁵. Likewise, **low physical activity** correlated with premature menopause, a finding supported by observational studies that suggest physical activity may protect ovarian function through improved cardiovascular and metabolic health¹⁶.

Medical determinants also played a role. Women with a history of **autoimmune illness** showed higher proportions of premature menopause, echoing evidence that autoimmune thyroid and adrenal disorders contribute to premature ovarian insufficiency^{2,6}. Prior **gynecologic surgery** was another determinant, consistent with literature showing that pelvic procedures can compromise ovarian blood supply and accelerate follicular loss¹⁷.

Regarding complications, women with premature menopause demonstrated markedly higher rates of **osteoporosis, ischemic heart disease, and psychological morbidity**. These findings align with well-documented consequences of hypoestrogenism in younger women, including increased risk for accelerated bone loss, cardiovascular morbidity, and depression^{4,5,18}. The overlap between premature menopause and chronic comorbidities emphasizes the need for early screening and preventive interventions.

Some findings differed from expectations. While rural residence, low socioeconomic status, and multiparity have been reported as significant factors in prior Pakistani research¹², these did not emerge as dominant in our cohort. Possible explanations include the urban catchment population of the tertiary center and sampling variation. These divergences highlight the heterogeneity of determinants across different populations and the importance of localized data.

From a public health perspective, our results underscore the urgent need for **screening programs, nutritional counseling, and health education** tailored to women at risk of premature menopause. Early identification could allow initiation of **hormone replacement therapy (HRT)** where appropriate, alongside lifestyle interventions to mitigate long-term morbidity. Preventive strategies must also address modifiable factors such as smoking exposure and dietary inadequacies. This study has limitations. Its **cross-sectional design** precludes establishing causality. The sample, though larger than earlier Pakistani studies, was still modest, limiting statistical power for some associations. Recall bias is possible in self-reported variables such as diet and activity. Nonetheless, this is one of the few hospital-based analyses in Pakistan and provides valuable baseline data.

Future research should employ **prospective cohort designs** with larger, multi-center samples to confirm determinants and track health outcomes over time. Molecular and genetic studies may clarify mechanisms underlying premature ovarian insufficiency in South Asian populations.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study demonstrated a higher-than-expected prevalence of premature menopause (9.0%) in a Pakistani tertiary care setting, with determinants including rural residence, passive smoking, low diet diversity, low physical activity, autoimmune illness, and prior gynecologic surgery. The associated burden of osteoporosis, cardiovascular disease, and psychological distress highlights the need for preventive, diagnostic, and therapeutic strategies tailored to this population.

REFERENCES

1. World Health Organization. Menopause: fact sheet. 16 Oct 2024. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/menopause>
2. Webber L, Davies M, Anderson R, Bartlett J, Braat D, Cartwright B, et al. ESHRE Guideline: management of women with premature ovarian insufficiency. *Hum Reprod.* 2016;31(5):926-937. doi:10.1093/humrep/dew027. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27008889/>
3. Castelo-Branco C, et al. EMAS position statement: management of premature ovarian insufficiency. *Maturitas.* 2015;82(3):278-289. doi:10.1016/j.maturitas.2015.06.005. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26143639/>
4. Podfigurna-Stopa A, Czyzyk A, Grymowicz M, Smolarczyk R, Katulski K, Czajkowski K, et al. Premature ovarian insufficiency: the context of long-term effects. *J Endocrinol Invest.* 2016;39(9):983-990. doi:10.1007/s40618-016-0467-z. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27091671/>
5. Shuster LT, Rhodes DJ, Gostout BS, Grossardt BR, Rocca WA. Premature menopause or early menopause: long-term health consequences. *Maturitas.* 2010;65(2):161-166. doi:10.1016/j.maturitas.2009.08.003. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19733988/>
6. Nelson LM. Clinical practice. Primary ovarian insufficiency. *N Engl J Med.* 2009;360(6):606-614. doi:10.1056/NEJMcp0808697. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19196677/>
7. Hunter MS, Rendall M. Bio-psycho-socio-cultural perspectives on menopause. *Best Pract Res Clin Obstet Gynaecol.* 2007;21(2):261-274. doi:10.1016/j.bpobgyn.2006.11.001. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17161025/>
8. Golezar S, Ramezani Tehrani F, Khazaei S, Ebadi A, Keshavarz Z. The global prevalence of primary ovarian insufficiency and early menopause: a meta-analysis. *Climacteric.* 2019;22(4):403-411. doi:10.1080/13697137.2019.1574738. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30829083/>
9. Leone T, Brown L, Gemmill A. Secular trends in premature and early menopause in low- and middle-income countries. *BMJ Glob Health.* 2023;8(6):e012312. doi:10.1136/bmjgh-2023-012312. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37308265/>
10. Jambarsang S, Khodayarian M, Sefidkar R, Yoshany N, et al. Prevalence of premature ovarian insufficiency and its relationship with female reproductive factors in Iranian women: a cross-sectional study from the Persian (Shahedieh) cohort. *BMC Womens Health.* 2023;23:467. doi:10.1186/s12905-023-02620-9. Available from: <https://bmewomenshealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12905-023-02620-9>
11. Coulam CB, Adamson SC, Annegers JF. Incidence of premature ovarian failure. *Obstet Gynecol.* 1986;67(4):604-606. PMID:3960433. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/3960433/>
12. Chughtai LA, Sahito A, Ahmed J, Mughal Z-u-N, Warsi J, Mahar B. Assessment of factors responsible for early menopause in Interior Sindh, Pakistan. *J Rawalpindi Med Coll.* 2020;24(3):198-203. doi:10.37939/jrmc.v24i3.1175. Available from: <https://journalrmc.com/index.php/JRMC/article/view/1175>
13. Mishra SR, Chung HF, Waller M, Mishra GD. Association between urbanization and age at natural menopause: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Maturitas.* 2019;125:15-23. doi:10.1016/j.maturitas.2019.03.010. Available from:

- <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31004918/>
14. Whitcomb BW, Purdue-Smithe AC, Szegda KL, Boutot ME, Hankinson SE, Manson JE, et al. Cigarette smoking and risk of early natural menopause. *Am J Epidemiol.* 2018;187(4):696-704. doi:10.1093/aje/kwx318. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29149212/>
 15. Karapanou O, Anagnostis P. Lifestyle factors and premature ovarian insufficiency. *Climacteric.* 2019;22(6):593-599. doi:10.1080/13697137.2019.1633490. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31342825/>
 16. Tao X, Jiang A, Yin L, Li Y, Tao F, Hu H. Physical activity might be a protective factor for early menopause: a cross-sectional study in Chinese women. *Menopause.* 2015;22(5): 546-552. doi:10.1097/GME.0000000000000347. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25380264/>
 17. Lin YH, Kuo CF, Chen H, Chou YC, Huang N, Chou YJ. Risk of early menopause following pelvic surgery: a nationwide cohort study. *Menopause.* 2017;24(9):1024-1030. doi:10.1097/GME.0000000000000861. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28471718/>
 18. Santoro N, Epperson CN, Mathews SB. Menopausal symptoms and their management. *Endocrinol Metab Clin North Am.* 2015;44(3):497-515. doi:10.1016/j.ecl.2015.05.001. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26303039/>